

“Developing language skills in English language classes in secondary schools”

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the problem of rising efficiency of secondary school's English lessons by paying more attention to the development of each language skills, listening, speaking, reading and writing.

Keywords: language skills, listening, speaking, reading, writing, active and passive language skills, facilitator, extensive reading, intensive reading.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы повышения эффективности занятий английским языком в общеобразовательных школах, уделяя особое внимание развитию каждого из языковых навыков, аудирования, говорения, чтения и письма.

Ключевые слова: языковые навыки, аудирование, говорение, чтение, письмо, активные и пассивные языковые навыки, фасилитатор, экстенсивное чтение, интенсивное чтение.

Language is the primary means of communication and communication between people around the world and for establishing good relations between

countries. It is no secret that in the modern world, English language stands out from other languages as a language used by more people living in different states, countries and regions. Today, it has become a leading language in many fields such as medicine, engineering, journalism, education, business, science, technology and mass media, pharmacology and scientific research. There are several factors that have brought English to the status of an international language. Due to the fact that most of the information on the Internet is in English, the demand for specialists who know this language and have the opportunity to get the necessary information from the websites in a timely manner is increasing day by day. Taking into account the above points, we can say that it is one of the urgent issues of today that Uzbek youth who are learning English as a foreign language should master this language thoroughly and become experts who can use it correctly. Taking this need into account, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev's address to the Oliy Majlis states, among other things: they wrote Indeed, a person who wants to do good and radiate light like the sun to people, should strive for perfection and master various sciences and professions. We would not be mistaken if we say that it is impossible to achieve such goals as our great grandfather said in the present era without learning foreign languages perfectly. In accordance with such a sharp demand, I suggest to make the study of physics and foreign languages a priority in the coming year."

In the modern world, where there is a great demand for the English language and for professionals who have mastered it well, its comprehensive study requires the careful formation of all skills. In order to master English at or near the level of native speakers, teachers in schools should organize exercises, assignments and lessons aimed at mastering all language skills in the educational process, and a

traditional teacher in the language learning process rather, he will have to play the role of a facilitator (helper). These language skills are: listening, speaking, reading, writing. Each of these skills is important for achieving the intended goal of language learning. Therefore, their mastery and development remains one of the necessary tasks of today. Listening comprehension and reading are considered passive (receptive) skills because they do not create language material, but rather they help to receive material created by others. Speaking and writing are active (creative) skills because students express their thoughts in the form of oral or written sentences with the help of language material. Thus, active and passive skills are not manifested at the same time. Listening before speaking is required, reading before writing (or vice versa).

If the language learner does not fully master each and use their capabilities properly, he may not be able to achieve the desired goal. At the same time, students should consider them equally important, because each of them is a separate, independent phenomenon related to language learning. In addition, teachers should use modern and advanced pedagogical technologies, methods and approaches in their lessons. Listening comprehension is the first skill to develop among the four skills. All skills are important, but listening comprehension is the most important. This is because it is the key to successful communication. Listening comprehension is a skill that develops faster than speaking, and it often affects reading and writing skills as well. Without well-developed and effective listening comprehension skills, language learners may not fully understand the message being conveyed and communication may not be successful. According to

Vandergrift, listening is a complex and active process in which the listener tries to compare what he hears with his prior knowledge. According to Hadfield, listening comprehension is the most difficult skill in learning a foreign language. It is no secret that many teachers do not pay enough attention to the development of listening comprehension skills. It should be said that when traditional lessons were given, this issue was not given any importance at all. Later, when non-traditional technologies began to develop, a slight shift in this regard was noticed. In this regard, Flowers and Miller say, "When assignments are given in the medium of the language being studied, language learners become immersed in that language." Listening comprehension, in particular, became one of the most important tools of the direct method, but it was not treated as a separate skill, as language learners repeated the same material. and inductive learning through repeated hearing were busy with, and teachers did not introduce tasks aimed at active listening comprehension into the teaching process. Similar situations were observed in other audio lingual and grammatical methods of language teaching. Later, the acquisition of listening comprehension was advanced to the level of language learners learning by interacting in real-life situations. In the period of high development of today's information media, it would be appropriate to use authentic materials widely in the formation of listening comprehension skills and development of skills in our country. The advantages of tasks aimed at teaching listening comprehension include:

- successful listening comprehension ensures full understanding of the language (situation);
- serves to speak fluently and fluently;

- helps students to correctly assess the speech situation;
- forms the ability of students to adequately respond to the opinions expressed by the interlocutor;
- helps to fully understand the content;
- useful in mastering new concepts and content presented in new material;
- helps to strengthen existing knowledge and skills;
- helps to gain the interlocutor's trust and respect.

In the lesson, the teacher can use many exercises and tasks aimed at developing students' listening comprehension skills. Listening and listening to various presentations, exhibitions, shows, TV shows, radio broadcasts presented in English outside the classroom will lead to a sharp improvement in listening comprehension skills. Speaking is an active skill and students need a lot of practice to develop it. Speaking is the most difficult skill to master when learning a foreign language, because the question asked during the conversation should be answered immediately. Effective communication in real conversation is possible only by practicing speaking a lot. Speaking is a skill that tests a language learner's knowledge in real-life situations. Even today, we can witness many teachers practicing repeating speech patterns and memorizing different texts and dialogues.

Speaking is one of the most difficult skills a language learner will face. Yet for many years it has been treated by us teachers as a secondary skill compared to reading, writing, and even listening comprehension skills.² When students are

required to speak English, they have a number of they face difficulties. They are afraid (embarrassed) to appear in front of the class, as a result, they try to get out of that situation as soon as possible (get rid of). In this situation, the teacher should motivate the students to speak without paying too much attention to their mistakes by giving them topics they are interested in, encouraging them. By developing speaking skills, you can have the following achievements:

- increase students' self-confidence;
- teaching students critical thinking and healthy thinking;
- teaching students to express their opinions freely and independently;
- teaching students to speak at various events;
- to be ready for interviews with different employers;
- to be ready to participate in discussions and debates;
- sell future products to customers;
- exchange of ideas when studying in groups and at international conferences;
- to continue studying at international universities;
- visiting countries of the world with different purposes;
- participation in international business forums;
- development of vocabulary and grammatical competences.

Reading. In most languages throughout human history, speaking and listening skills were first developed. After a long time, writing and reading skills have also

begun to form. It is natural for young children to start talking after listening to and listening to the conversations of adults. Later, they will have to develop speaking skills such as reading and writing. All this happens in the process of children learning their mother tongue. When learning foreign languages, children begin to master all skills at the same time. There are two types of reading: extensive and intensive reading. Extensive reading occurs when a person reads for pleasure. This type of reading is convenient for language learners to choose and study according to their own preferences. Through extensive reading, language learners can improve their reading skills. Because this method is an effective way to develop language learners' vocabulary and grammatical competence, it is advisable for teachers to engage their students in as much reading as possible. It's no secret that today's youth are doing less writing because they have smartphones and other electronic devices connected to the Internet that provide them with ready-made texts and instant answers. They are spending their valuable time searching for what others have done (written) rather than developing their writing skills. It is also clear that students with well-developed writing skills are more successful than others in expressing their independent opinions and achieving their goals. In conclusion, it can be said that as the position and prestige of the English language in the world community is increasing, it should be learned in our country as well. It is important to fully master each of the four skills that play a key role in learning English. These skills are listening, speaking, reading and writing (TLS), and effective language acquisition requires the development of all of them. Systematization and planning of the process of teaching foreign languages through the development of language skills requires the training of foreign language teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications.

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